

Rayleigh-Taylor Instability with a delta-SPH multiphase formulation: comparison with linear stability analysis

Jon Martinez-Carrascal

Leo Miguel González
Model Basin Research Group (CEHINAV)
Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM)
Madrid , Spain
jon.martinez@upm.es

Javier Calderon-Sanchez

Abstract—The Rayleigh-Taylor instability (RTI) is present in numerous physical processes such as the plasma dynamics or the vertical sloshing inside fuel tanks. This physical instability has been analytically quantified for the horizontally periodic case with and without limitations in the vertical direction. The influence of the finite domain, surface tension and viscosity on the growth rate evolution has been deeply studied as an eigenvalue problem.

The aim of this work is to use a multiphase δ -SPH formulation to perform a complete simulation of the RTI and compare the growth rate of the linear part of the instability with the linear stability analysis of the problem when the structure of the eigenvectors match the first stages of the velocity field. Previous SPH simulations performed mainly focus on qualitative results and the robustness of the formulation. In this work, a detailed quantitative validation of our multiphase SPH formulation in terms of the slope of the growing velocity magnitude is performed. This kind of validation of a purely Lagrangian formulation such as SPH is quite novel in the literature and gives SPH important credits in terms of numerical description of a complex physical phenomenon. The comparison is performed for a wide range of viscosity and density combinations even when surface tension is added to the formulation. Furthermore, the influence of no-slip and periodic boundary conditions is investigated and compared to the stability analysis results.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Rayleigh-Taylor instability (RTI) appears when a heavy fluid overlies a lighter fluid [22], [28] and gravity is oriented towards the light fluid, i.e. the density gradient and gravity are opposed. This situation is present in a wide variety of applications: ferrofluids [23], tectonics [14], exploding foils [30], aerobreakup [29], and astrophysics [3], [27]. An original extension of the RTI appears in the sloshing phenomena when two different fluids are confined in an accelerated tank [16]. In this case, the light fluid overlies a heavier fluid when gravity is present, but the RTI appears when a larger acceleration than gravity is applied to both fluids in the opposite direction to the force of gravity. As explained before, the density gradient is opposed to the difference between the inertial force and gravity.

Mikaelian [17] analyzed the Rayleigh-Taylor instability in

two finite-thickness fluids taking viscosity effects into account. A numerical dispersion relation was obtained for different thicknesses and Atwood numbers. He performed a 1D analysis based on two fluids separated with a sharp interface using homogeneous Dirichlet and Neumann conditions for the velocity at the top and bottom boundaries, and compatibility conditions at the interface. The 2D extension presented in this work allows the analysis of more complex flows and includes the possibility of studying diffuse interfaces, the sharp interface just being a particular case.

In order to confirm the findings, the RTI is also reproduced using the meshless Lagrangian method Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH), that is gaining significant attention in the last decades according to its ability to deal with complex physics and complex geometries, such as the field of fluid dynamics involving free-surface flows. SPH exhibits significant advantages when compared to other methods, such as Finite Volumes or Finite Elements when dealing with multiphase flow, because density is transported by the particles and there is no need to include an additional scalar transport equation. The transport of scalar functions by advection equations performed in formulations such as Volume of Fluid (VOF) or Level Set is not a numerically trivial problem that normally implies dispersion and diffusion numerical errors and loss of interface sharpness. In this particular situation a multiphase formulation is required, which implies the necessity of a modern and robust WCSPH version [13]. Most of the literature addressing the RTI problem with SPH normally focus on the evolution of the flow and the robustness of the numerical formulation, but very few compare the growth rates with other results from the stability analysis. Some of the first attempts correspond to [8] and [26], using Incompressible (ISPH) and Weakly Compressible (WCSPH) approaches respectively. Works on multiphase SPH developed by [12], [25] or [19] present results for the Rayleigh-Taylor problem to validate their different multiphase SPH or surface tension formulations, but these are only analyzed from a qualitative perspective in terms of free-surface evolution at certain characteristic time instants.

A further step is performed in the work by [24], where some

comparison with approximate solutions to the classical stability analysis is performed. In contrast to the work presented here, the initial free surface is deformed instead of initialized with a velocity field. In that study, a quantitative analysis of the growth rate of the RTI in a confined geometry is carried out for a single instability mode and a single Atwood number. The analysis focuses on the dependence of the problem with the surface tension.

In this paper the following new ideas are proposed: first, a general 2D formulation is presented to analyze the RTI that considers the possibility of using density- and viscosity-regularized fluids, geometrical flexibility, alternative boundary conditions and surface tension implementation. In particular, the possibility of using no slip lateral boundary conditions allows for the analysis of a completely confined tank, and also the quantification of the differences with the well known periodic VRTI spectrum. Second, we want to confirm that a meshless lagrangian numerical method such as WCSPH is able to reproduce the dynamics observed in this particular multiphase problem with reasonable accuracy.

The paper is organised as follows: in section II the general description of the RTI is explained and the general equations are presented. In section III the used SPH formulation is detailed. In section IV, the results obtained for the RTI problem with different boundary conditions are monitored and compared to reference solutions. Finally, conclusions are presented in section V.

II. MATHEMATICAL MODEL

The strategies to perform the linear stability analysis are presented in this section. To study the viscous version of the Rayleigh-Taylor instability, we assume a zero velocity base-flow and regularized density and viscosity distributions that represent two fluids separated by a common interface. We analyze the evolution of the perturbations by the assumed base-flow. In particular, we are interested in the development of two-dimensional flow structures and the growth rates of the different unstable modes. The calculations have been performed in a 2D computational domain. Previous validations of the viscous and inviscid cases without surface tension in 1D and 2D geometries can be found in [11].

Let ρ_1, μ_1, ν_1 and ρ_2, μ_2, ν_2 be the densities, and the kinematic and dynamic viscosities of the top-(heavy) and bottom-(light) fluids respectively. The two phase flow is governed by the incompressible Newtonian Navier-Stokes equations in a domain Ω in the presence of gravity g , which imply mass and momentum conservation, and a density transport equation. As the velocity baseflow is zero, the viscosity transport equation is not necessary in this RTI formulation, see [15]. The domain will be a rectangle of height $2H$ and width $2L$ contained on the XY plane, mathematically expressed as $\Omega = [-L, L] \times [-H, H]$ (see Figure 1).

Similarly to [6], the characteristic time, length, velocity, pressure, density and viscosity scales used to transform the problem to its non-dimensional version are defined as:

Fig. 1. Outlines of the computational geometry used for the Rayleigh-Taylor simulations. A dashed line at $y = 0$ indicates the interface between fluids. The boundary conditions are also written at each boundary for both cases: periodic (top) and tank (bottom) configurations.

$$\rho_o = \frac{\rho_1 + \rho_2}{2} \quad \mu_o = \frac{\mu_1 + \mu_2}{2} \quad \nu_o = \frac{\nu_1 + \nu_2}{2}, \quad (1)$$

$$t_o = (\nu_o/g^2)^{1/3} \quad l_o = (\nu_o^2/g)^{1/3} \quad u_o = (g\nu_o)^{1/3}, \quad (2)$$

$$k_o = (\nu_o^2/g)^{-1/3} \quad p_o = \rho_o g (\nu_o^2/g)^{1/3} \quad (3)$$

The non-dimensional version of this set of equations reads:

$$\rho \frac{\partial \vec{u}}{\partial t} + \rho \vec{u} \cdot \nabla \vec{u} = -\nabla p + \rho \vec{u}_g + \nabla [\mu (\nabla \vec{u} + \nabla \vec{u}^T)], \quad (4)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{u} = 0, \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \vec{u} \cdot \nabla \rho = 0 \quad (6)$$

where $\rho, \vec{u}, p, t, \nabla, \mu, \tau, \vec{u}_g$ are the non-dimensional density, velocity, pressure, time, nabla operator, viscosity, viscous stress tensor and unity vector representing gravity.

A steady nonparallel basic flow $(\bar{u}_i, \bar{\rho}, \bar{p})$ is perturbed by small-amplitude velocity \tilde{u}_i , density $\tilde{\rho}$ and pressure \tilde{p} perturbations, as follows:

$$u_i(x, y, z, t) = \bar{u}_i(x, y) + \varepsilon \tilde{u}_i(x, y, z, t) + c.c. \quad (7)$$

$$p(x, y, z, t) = \bar{p}(x, y) + \varepsilon \tilde{p}(x, y, z, t) + c.c. \quad (8)$$

$$\rho(x, y, z, t) = \bar{\rho}(x, y) + \varepsilon \tilde{\rho}(x, y, z, t) + c.c. \quad (9)$$

where $\varepsilon \ll 1$, and $c.c$ denotes the conjugate of the complex quantities $\tilde{u}_i, \tilde{\rho}$ and \tilde{p} . As baseflow, we consider two superposed fluids at rest $\bar{u}_i = 0$ separated by a regularized interface at $y = 0$ and subjected to a constant gravitational acceleration pointing downwards the vertical direction y .

Therefore, in order to describe the RTI of a sharp interface, it seems more consistent to attempt to solve the problem

for a transition layer of finite thickness, and then take the limit when the thickness tends to zero. Similarly to the sharp jump implementation used in [11], we adopt the density and viscosity profiles

$$\bar{\rho} = 1 + A_\rho \tanh(y/L_s) \quad \mu = 1 + A_\mu \tanh(y/L_s) \quad (10)$$

where L_s is the gradient scale length of the density and viscosity layers and A_ρ, A_μ the Atwood numbers given by

$$A_\rho = \frac{\rho_1 - \rho_2}{\rho_1 + \rho_2} \quad A_\mu = \frac{\mu_1 - \mu_2}{\mu_1 + \mu_2} \quad (11)$$

Taking account of equations (10), typical air-water hydrodynamic instabilities in the presence of a sharp interface can be recovered by setting $L_s \rightarrow 0$. When equations (7), (8) and (9) are substituted into the Navier-Stokes equations (4), (5) and 6, assuming zero base flow $\bar{u}_i = 0$ and neglecting second order terms, the linearized Navier-Stokes equations for the perturbation quantities are obtained:

$$\bar{\rho} \frac{\partial \tilde{u}_i}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial \tilde{p}}{\partial x_i} + \mu \Delta \hat{u}_i + \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{u}_j}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial \tilde{u}_i}{\partial x_j} \right) \frac{\partial \mu}{\partial x_j} + \tilde{\rho} u_{g_i} \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{\rho}}{\partial t} + \tilde{u}_j \frac{\partial \tilde{\rho}}{\partial x_j} = 0 \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{u}_i}{\partial x_i} = 0 \quad (14)$$

Since the coefficients of $\tilde{u}_i, \tilde{\rho}$ and \tilde{p} do not depend on z and t the perturbation quantities can be written as normal modes:

$$\tilde{u}_i(x, y, z, t) = \hat{u}_i(x, y) e^{ik_z z} e^{\gamma t} + \text{c.c.} \quad (15)$$

$$\tilde{p}(x, y, z, t) = \hat{p}(x, y) e^{ik_z z} e^{\gamma t} + \text{c.c.} \quad (16)$$

$$\tilde{\rho}(x, y, z, t) = \hat{\rho}(x, y) e^{ik_z z} e^{\gamma t} + \text{c.c.} \quad (17)$$

where the complex conjugate (c.c.) is required to render the perturbations real. Additionally, $\gamma = \sigma + i\omega \in \mathbb{C}$ is the complex growth/decay rate σ and oscillation frequency ω .

Let us add the presence of the surface tension on the free surface that separates both fluid phases to this perturbed system. Following [6], the surface tension presence adds the term $-2(\partial_{xx} \hat{\xi}_s - k_z^2 \hat{\xi}_s) S \delta_s(y - y_s)$ to the y projection of the equation (12), where $\hat{\xi}_s = \hat{\xi}(x, y_s) e^{ik_z z} e^{\gamma t}$ is the vertical displacement of the free surface at $y = y_s$, $\delta_s(y - y_s)$ is the Dirac's delta function and S is the non-dimensional surface tension, which can be expressed as:

$$S = \frac{T_s}{(\rho_1 + \rho_2)(g\nu^4)^{1/3}} \quad (18)$$

with T_s being the dimensional surface tension. In order to proceed with the numerical integration, the Dirac delta function will be regularized and the term $\hat{\xi}$ can be related to the vertical velocity perturbation \hat{v} as:

$$\hat{v} = \frac{\partial \hat{\xi}}{\partial t} = \gamma \hat{\xi} \quad (19)$$

III. SPH FORMULATION

One of the objectives of this work is to prove that the SPH formulation is a valid tool to perform a stability analysis of the RTI. For that purpose, we are going to discretize the set of equations 4 using the multiphase δ -WCSPH formulation detailed in [13]. The software used is AQUAgpusph, an open source SPH code based on GPU capabilities. The discretized set of equations reads:

$$\frac{dV_i}{dt} = V_i(\mathbf{u}_i - \mathbf{u}_j) \cdot \nabla W_{ij} V_i + \delta h c_{0_x} \sum_{j \in \chi} \mathbf{D}_{ij}^V \cdot \nabla W_{ij} V_j \quad (20)$$

$$\rho_i \frac{d\mathbf{u}_i}{dt} = - \sum_j (p_i + p_j) \nabla W_{ij} V_j + \rho_i \mathbf{g} + \nabla^2 \mathbf{u}_i + \mathbf{\Omega}_i \quad (21)$$

$$\frac{d\mathbf{r}_i}{dt} = \mathbf{u}_i \quad (22)$$

$$\rho_i = \sum_{j \in \chi} m_j W_{ij}^S \quad (23)$$

$$p_i = \frac{\rho_{0_x} c_{0_x}^2}{\gamma_x} \left(\left(\frac{\rho_i}{\rho_{0_x}} \right)^{\gamma_x} - 1 \right) + p_b \quad (24)$$

This set of equations is composed of a volume conservation equation 20, a momentum conservation equation 21, a time evolution of the trajectory of each particle 22, an evaluation of the density field 23 and an equation of state 24. Where V_j accounts for the volume of the neighbor particles j and $W_{ij} = W(\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i, h)$ and $\nabla_i W_{ij} = \nabla W(\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i, h)$ represent the kernel function and its derivative with respect to the i -th particle, at constant h , respectively. In this work, a Wendland C2 kernel with $h/dr = 2$ is used, where h and dr correspond to the smoothing length and the particle distance respectively. The dissipation effects due to viscosity are grouped in the $\nabla^2 \mathbf{u}$ term which is defined as:

$$\nabla^2 \mathbf{u}_i = \mu_\chi \sum_{j \in \chi} \pi_{ij} \nabla W_{ij} V_j \quad (25)$$

where the function π_{ij} , reads as:

$$\pi_{ij} = \frac{(\mathbf{u}_j - \mathbf{u}_i) \cdot (\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i)}{\|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i\|^2} \quad (26)$$

In the volume conservation equation, an additional term is added to avoid spurious high-frequency pressure oscillations, following the work by [1] and extended to the multiphase formulation by [13]. An additional term of this form has actually become a standard in SPH, and this particular model is the so called δ -SPH. The term \mathbf{D}_{ij}^V is defined as:

$$\mathbf{D}_{ij}^V = V_i \left[2 \left(1 - \frac{\rho_j}{\rho_i} \right) - \frac{1}{\rho_i} \left(\langle \nabla \rho \rangle_j^L + \langle \nabla \rho \rangle_i^L \right) \cdot (\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i) \right] \frac{(\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i)}{\|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i\|^2} \quad (27)$$

where $\langle \nabla \rho \rangle_i^L$ represents the renormalized density gradient, as defined by [21]. The value for δ is set always to 0.1. Note

that the sum of the neighbours is extended to neighbouring particles of the same phase $j \in \chi$.

In the momentum conservation equation, ρ is the fluid density, \mathbf{g} represents the gravity, $\mathbf{\Omega}$ the surface tension force, p the pressure and μ_χ is the dynamic viscosity of phase χ . The flow velocity, \mathbf{u} , is defined as the material derivative of a fluid particle position, \mathbf{r} .

In order to close the system of equations in 20-23 a stiff equation of state is needed (equation 24). In this work a polytropic equation of state is used where γ_χ is the polytropic exponent of phase χ , $\rho_{0\chi}$ represents the reference density of phase χ and p_b represents the background pressure that is set to $p_b = 1$ Pa in all simulations presented in this work. The compressibility of the phase can be adjusted artificially by changing the speed of sound of the phase $c_{0\chi}$ [2].

As the continuity equation is expressed in terms of volume, density is evaluated with a summation formula 23 within phase χ . According to this, the kernel W_{ij}^S is defined for each phase as:

$$W_{ij}^S = \frac{W_{ij}}{\sum_{k \in \chi} W_{ik} V_k} \quad (28)$$

Time integration is performed by means of a predictor-corrector scheme [5]. The Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) condition is set to 0.1 to assure time stability.

When surface tension is taken into account an additional term $\mathbf{\Omega}$ is added to the momentum equation in equation 21 to deal with effects at the interface. This force has been included in SPH in the same fashion as in [18], and the expression reads:

$$\mathbf{\Omega}_i = -\frac{T_s}{\rho_i} \sum_j (\mathbf{n}_j - \mathbf{n}_i) \cdot \nabla W_{ij} V_j \mathbf{n}_i \quad (29)$$

where T_s is the surface tension coefficient and \mathbf{n}_i represents the local normal vector to the interface of particle i .

Both periodical and wall boundary conditions are set in the corresponding numerical tests carried out in this work.

Periodical boundary conditions are defined such that every generic field f satisfies

$$f(x)|_{\partial\Omega_1} = f(x)|_{\partial\Omega_2} \quad (30)$$

For wall boundary conditions, either slip or no-slip conditions can be imposed.

Boundary integrals methodology is used in this work. The formulation employed here is based on the works by [10] solving these numerically as explained by [5] with the semi-analytical expressions for the kernel obtained by [4] based on [9]

No-slip boundary conditions are imposed at the discrete level in the same fashion as described by [7] for the boundary integrals formulation, such that:

Fig. 2. Qualitative comparison between the snapshots of the SPH simulation at $t/t_0 = 5$ and the amplitude perturbation of the velocity components (non dimensional) of the most unstable eigenvector for the case $k = \pi$, $2H = 2$, $2L = 8$ and $A_\mu = A_\rho = 0.6$. The 2D fields represented are vertical velocity (a,c) and horizontal velocity (b,d).

$$\left\langle \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial \mathbf{n}} \right\rangle = \sum_{j \in BE} \left[\frac{(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{n}_j \otimes \mathbf{n}_j) \mathbf{u}_{ji}}{|\mathbf{r}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{n}_j|} \right] W_{ij} V_i S_j. \quad (31)$$

IV. RESULTS

A. Periodic BCs

In this section the RTI will be simulated using the non-linear SPH multiphase formulation, see Section III. Most numerical approaches to the simulation of the RTI are normally limited to snapshots of the flow evolution and the confirmation of the robustness and speed of the multiphase formulation. Very few SPH approaches [20], [24] contain a detailed quantitative comparison to other classical numerical formulations where well established results such as the growth rate of the linear part of the VRTI are monitored. Consequently, the objective of this section is not only to present the results of the SPH formulation, but also to compare the initial evolution of the SPH solution with the results presented by the 1D spectral validated formulation in terms of growth rate. The comparison will be performed for a wide range of Atwood and wavenumbers, with and without surface tension.

To perform this task, a fixed point with coordinates $(x, y) = (0, H/10)$, is selected to monitor the evolution of the interpolated velocity of the surrounding particles. To trigger the RTI, an initial perturbation $\hat{v}_0(x, y)$ of magnitude $\epsilon \ll \sqrt{gH}$ is added to the initial flow. This perturbation is horizontally periodic with a wavenumber k and exponentially decaying on the vertical axis, and consequently we expect to trigger the instability associated with that particular wavenumber. The expression of the initial vertical velocity perturbation is:

$$\hat{v}_0(x, y) = \epsilon \cos(kx) \exp\left(-\left|\frac{y}{(y+H)(y-H)}\right|\right) \quad (32)$$

In Figure 2 a qualitative comparison between the amplitude perturbation of the velocity components (non dimensional) of the most unstable eigenvector when the stability problem is solved [11] and a snapshot of the evolution of the velocity

Fig. 3. Comparison of the evolution of the velocity at $(x, y) = (0, H/10)$ when the SPH simulations are compared to the linear stability analysis results represented by the dotted lines for $A_\rho = A_\mu = 0.6$ and $k = \pi$ (red) and $k = 3\pi/4$ (blue).

Fig. 4. Growth rate of the vertical velocity at the fixed point $x = 0, y = H/10$ versus wavenumber for different values of the density Atwood number $A_\mu = 0, 2H = 4$ and $2L = 1$. The growth rate is compared to the values predicted by the linear stability analysis theory [17].

fields is shown at time $t/t_0 = 5$, when the initial flow is excited with $k = \pi$ and both Atwood numbers are equal $A_\rho = A_\mu = 0.6$ are shown. At this time step, the velocity field is immersed in the linear regime after the initial oscillations caused by the combination of the particle setup and the weakly compressible assumption. It is worth noting that the velocity perturbations corresponding to the most unstable mode obtained after the linear stability analysis, exhibit a good matching with the velocity snapshots.

An example of the time evolution of the velocity for the case with $A_\rho = A_\mu = 0.6$ and wave numbers $k = 3\pi/4$ and $k = \pi$ is shown in Figure 3. As can be seen, at the beginning the initial perturbation is hidden behind the noise created by the pressure field trying to satisfy the weakly compressible assumption which creates a few oscillations. Once the particles have settled down and the pressure field stabilizes $t/t_0 \sim 1.5$, the perturbation triggers the VRTI and the system evolves in time with a clean, growing linear regime. As can be observed in the figure, the slope of this signal is parallel to the growth rate computed by the linear stability analysis, which indicates excellent matching with the linear theory.

A complete comparison between the growth rates obtained

Fig. 5. Comparison of the evolution of the velocity at $(x, y) = (0, H/10)$ when the initial state of the SPH simulation is perturbed with $k = \pi/4$. Results are compared to three reference results of the linear stability analysis represented by the dotted lines for $A_\rho = A_\mu = 0.6$ and $k = \pi/4, \pi/2$ and $3\pi/4$

from the transient slopes of the SPH simulations and the corresponding values obtained from the linear stability analysis is shown in Figure 4. The comparison is performed using eight wave numbers in the interval $k \in [0, 2\pi]$ and four density-viscosity Atwood numbers $A_\rho = A_\mu = 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8$. With the exception of a very few points obtained for the largest Atwood number, the agreement obtained is reasonable and the maximum of each curve is always detected at $k \approx 3\pi/4$. The detection and identification of the slopes of the linear intervals during the SPH simulation is a numerically sensitive task that can also be considered a source of error.

Figure 5 represents what occurs when the wave number of the initial perturbation $k = \pi/4$ is not close to the wave number $k_{max} \approx 3\pi/4$ that gives the maximum growth rate of the instability. After the adaptation interval, three clearly distinguishable slopes are present with a transient between them showing that the dynamical evolution of the linear system jumps from the perturbed mode to the next most unstable mode until it reaches k_{max} . The first slope matches the growth rate of the initial excitation $k = \pi/4$, but around time $t/t_0 \sim 7.4$, the system evolves to the second mode with $k = \pi/2$ and then at $t/t_0 \sim 12$ it finally jumps to the wave number that gives the maximum growth rate at $k = k_{max} = 3\pi/4$. In Figure 6 the growth rate of the perturbation is represented against the density Atwood number $A_\rho \in [0.1, 0.9]$ for the case $2H = 2, 2L = 8$ and $k = 3\pi/4$, for $A_\rho = A_\mu$. As can be appreciated the agreement with the results presented in [17] is excellent. For high Atwood numbers $A_\rho \geq 0.9$, the match between the SPH calculations and the linear stability analysis worsens due to the large density gradients involved in the calculations.

When the SPH surface tension model described in Section III is added to the problem, the SPH results still obtain a good prediction and capture the instability reduction due to the surface tension contribution, see Figure 7. Alternatively, a second simplified implementation of the surface tension was

Fig. 6. Growth rate versus density Atwood number obtained in a computational domain $2H = 8$, $2L = 2$, $A_\mu = A_\rho$ and $k = 3\pi/4$. The values predicted by reference [17] are also plotted for comparison.

Fig. 7. Growth rate versus wave number for $A_\rho = A_\mu = 0.6$ with and without surface tension. The growth rate is compared to the values predicted by the linear stability analysis theory.

also performed in SPH. We can consider that the presence of surface tension is equivalent to a gravity reduction given by the equation:

$$g_S = g \left(1 - \frac{k^2 S}{A_\rho} \right) \quad (33)$$

where g_S is the gravity value when the surface tension S is included in the model and the second derivative has been replaced by $-k^2$ assuming during this linear stage a horizontal periodicity of the flow with the same wave number as the initial excitation. This simplification is only valid for comparing the results during the linear regime also computed by the stability analysis, and no realistic results are expected during the nonlinear evolution of the SPH simulation. However, the results obtained by this simplified implementation of the surface tension approximate the ones from the linear theory very well, with a small underprediction for the largest growth rate.

In Figure 7 the case without surface tension has been added to the graph to observe the stability decreases for large wave numbers when surface tension is present, showing that the surface tension has a stabilizing effect on the RTI.

Fig. 8. Growth rate of the vertical velocity at the fixed point $(x, y) = (0, H/10)$ for different values of the density and viscosity Atwood numbers $A_\mu = A_\rho$, $2H = 2$ and 4 , $2L = 8$ and 1 . The growth rate is compared to the values predicted by the linear stability analysis theory.

B. Confined tank

The same linear stability analysis that has been performed for periodic boundary conditions can be solved with no-slip velocity boundary conditions in the right and left boundaries at $x = \pm L$, see the bottom part of Figure 1. As a non-periodic assumption is allowed in the horizontal direction, the results of this analysis cannot be compared any more using the classical 1D spectral stability analysis, see [11], and can only be compared against a 2D solution. The solutions obtained in this subsection will be computed for two geometries, the first one being $(2H, 2L) = (2, 8)$ and the second being $(2H, 2L) = (4, 1)$.

An important observation when no slip boundary conditions are used in a domain with horizontal fixed length is that we cannot assume a clear spatial periodicity in the horizontal direction, and consequently no wave number can be associated to the different modes. This clearly indicates that changing the lateral boundary conditions implies the absence of horizontal periodicity.

The SPH formulation will be applied to the no-slip case which is representative to the one found in tanks. In order to compare this with the linear stability analysis, the baseflow is excited according to the following expression:

$$\hat{v}_0(x, y) = \epsilon \sin(kx) \exp \left(- \left| \frac{y}{(y+H)(y-H)} \right| \right) \quad (34)$$

where the initial perturbation \hat{v}_0 has been selected in order to satisfy the no-slip boundary condition at $x = \pm L$. In Figure 8, the growth rates obtained measuring the slope of the linear velocity growth at $(x, y) = (0, H/10)$ are compared, for different Atwood numbers, to the most unstable eigenvalue obtained from the linear analysis of both geometries. For the sake of simplicity, both the viscosity and density Atwood numbers were equal $A_\rho = A_\mu$. As can be observed, excellent agreement is obtained for all Atwood numbers. In order to confirm the reduction in terms of growth rate, the previous results with periodic boundary conditions are also plotted in Figure 8. As expected from the comparison performed using

the linear stability analysis in [11], the linear part presents a lower growth rate (smaller eigenvalue) than the periodic version. We conclude that the presence of the lateral walls decreases the growth rate of the VRTI as they increase the viscous action and this decrease in growth rate is accentuated for higher Atwood numbers.

V. CONCLUSION

The most important conclusions obtained in this work are the following:

- The RTI problem has been simulated with the WCSPH method in a multiphase framework. This method is clearly non-linear but is able to capture the linear regime that is present at the first stage of the simulation. The multiphase SPH formulation presents a robust stability for a wide range of densities and viscosities, gives the possibility of implementing both the no-slip and the periodic boundary conditions, and contains a surface tension model for the interface.
- The classical 1D formulation is limited to those cases where the horizontal coordinate is periodic, in contrast with the 2D formulation assumed here, which permits studying more general cases, as for example those cases where the fluids are confined and no-slip boundary conditions are necessary for the lateral walls. This situation appears in engineering applications as a Rayleigh-Taylor instability, which is frequently found in accelerating fuel tanks.
- The matching between WCSPH and linear stability analysis is very good in a relevant range of wavenumbers, indicating that a lagrangian formulation is able to predict not only the growth rate values and the corresponding structures identified with the eigenvalues and the eigenvectors of the generalized LNSE, but also captures the evolution of the internal dynamics of the different growing modes involved in the Rayleigh-Taylor instability.
- The comparison between confined and periodic geometries displays a decrease in the growth rate that is assumed to come from the viscous action present in the lateral walls of the problem.
- The 2D formulation allows for performing the same analysis in more complex geometries than the simple rectangular tank used here, or even in realistic baffled fuel tanks like the ones used in the aircraft industry.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The research leading to these results was undertaken as part of the SLOWD project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 815044. Leo M. González acknowledges the financial support from the Spanish Ministry for Science, Innovation and Universities (MCIU) under grant RTI2018-096791-B-C21 *Hidrodinámica de elementos de amortiguamiento del movimiento de aerogeneradores flotantes*. All the authors would like to thank Mr.

Ciaran Stone for his valuable assistance during the preparation of this manuscript. This research has also received funding from Universidad Politécnica de Madrid under a pre-doctoral scholarship.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Antuono, A. Colagrossi, and S. Marrone. Numerical diffusive terms in weakly-compressible sph schemes. *Computer Physics Communications*, 2012.
- [2] M. Antuono, A. Colagrossi, S. Marrone, and D. Molteni. Free-surface flows solved by means of SPH schemes with numerical diffusive terms. *Computer Physics Communications*, 2010.
- [3] A. A. Blinova, M. M. Romanova, and R. V. E. Lovelace. Boundary between stable and unstable regimes of accretion. ordered and chaotic unstable regimes. *Mon. Not. R. Astron. Soc.*, 459:2354, 2016.
- [4] J. Calderon-Sanchez, J.L. Cercos-Pita, and D. Duque. A geometric formulation of the shepard renormalization factor. *Computers & Fluids*, 183:16 – 27, 2019.
- [5] Jose L Cercos-Pita. Aquagpusph, a new free 3D SPH solver accelerated with OpenCL. *Computer Physics Communications*, 192:295–312, 2015.
- [6] S. Chandrasekhar. *Hydrodynamic and Hydromagnetic Stability*. Dover, New-York, 1981.
- [7] L Chiron, Matthieu De Lefte, Guillaume Oger, and David Le Touzé. Fast and accurate sph modelling of 3d complex wall boundaries in viscous and non viscous flows. *Computer Physics Communications*, 234:93–111, 2019.
- [8] SJ Cummins and M Rudman. An sph projection method. *J. Comput. Phys.*, 152:584, 1999.
- [9] J Feldman and J Bonet. Dynamic refinement and boundary contact forces in SPH with applications in fluid flow problems. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, 72(3):295–324, 2007.
- [10] M. Ferrand, D.R. Laurence, B.D. Rogers, D. Violeau, and C. Kassiotis. Unified semi-analytical wall boundary conditions for inviscid laminar or turbulent flows in the meshless SPH method. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Fluids*, 2013.
- [11] L. M. González-Gutiérrez and A. de Andrea González. Numerical computation of the rayleigh-taylor instability for a viscous fluid with regularized interface properties. *Phys. Review E*, 100:013101, 2019.
- [12] Nicolas Grenier, Matteo Antuono, Andrea Colagrossi, David Le Touzé, and B Alessandrini. An hamiltonian interface sph formulation for multi-fluid and free surface flows. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 228(22):8380–8393, 2009.
- [13] I. Hammani, S. Marrone, A. Colagrossi, and G. Oger. Extension of the δ -SPH model to multi-phase flow. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 2020.
- [14] C. Harig, P. Molnar, and G. A. Houseman. Rayleigh-Taylor instability under a shear stress free top boundary condition and its relevance to removal of mantle lithosphere from beneath the sierra nevada. *Tectonics*, 27:TC6019, 2008.
- [15] R. Hide. The character of the equilibrium of a heavy, viscous, incompressible, rotating fluids of variable density. i. general theory. *Quart. J. Mech. Appl. Math.*, 9:22–34, 1955.
- [16] J. Martinez-Carrascal and L. M. González-Gutiérrez. Experimental study of the liquid damping effects on a sdf vertical sloshing tank. *Journal of Fluids and Structures*, 2021.
- [17] K. O. Mikaelian. Rayleigh-Taylor instability in finite-thickness fluids with viscosity and surface tension. *Phys. Rev. E*, 54(4):3676, 1996.
- [18] Joseph P. Morris. Simulating surface tension with smoothed particle hydrodynamics. *Numerical Methods in Fluids*, 2000.
- [19] Shadloo MS and Yildiz M. ISPH modelling of rayleigh-taylor instability. In *6th international SPHERIC workshop proceedings*, 2011.
- [20] A. Rahmat, N. Tofghi, M.S. Shadloo, and M. Yildiz. Numerical simulation of wall bounded and electrically excited rayleigh-taylor instability using incompressible smoothed particle hydrodynamics. *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochem. Eng. Aspects*, 460:60–70, 2014.
- [21] P. W. Randles and L. D. Libersky. Smoothed particle hydrodynamics: Some recent improvements and applications. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, 1996.
- [22] Lord Rayleigh. Investigation of the character of the equilibrium of an incompressible heavy fluid of variable density. *Proc. London Math Soc.*, s1-14(1):170–177, 1883.

- [23] R. E. Rosensweig, Y. Hirota, S. Tsuda, and K. Raj. Study of audio speakers containing ferrofluid. *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter*, 20:204147, 2008.
- [24] MS Shadloo, Amir Zainali, and M Yildiz. Simulation of single mode rayleigh–taylor instability by sph method. *Computational Mechanics*, 51(5):699–715, 2013.
- [25] K. Szewc, A. Tanière, and J.P. Minier. A study on application of smoothed particle hydrodynamics to multi-phase flows. *International Journal of Nonlinear Sciences and Numerical Simulation*, 13(6):383–395, 2012.
- [26] Alexandre M Tartakovsky and Paul Meakin. A smoothed particle hydrodynamics model for miscible flow in three-dimensional fractures and the two-dimensional rayleigh–taylor instability. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 207(2):610–624, 2005.
- [27] A. Tavakoli, L. Hadzievski, and D. D. Tskhakayab. Rayleigh-Taylor instability of magnetized density transition layer. *Phys. Plasmas*, 7(1):89–93, 1999.
- [28] G. I. Taylor. Instability of liquid surfaces when accelerated in a direction perpendicular to their planes. *Proc. R. Soc. London*, 192:201, 1950.
- [29] T. G. Theofanous. Aerobreakup of newtonian and viscoelastic liquids. *Annu. Rev. Fluid Mech.*, 43:661, 2011.
- [30] T. M. Willey, K. Champley, R. Hodgin, L. Lauderbach, M. Bagge-Hansen, C. May, N. Sanchez, B. J. Jensen, A. Iverson, and T. van Buuren. X-ray imaging and 3d reconstruction of in-flight exploding foil initiation flyers. *J. Appl. Phys.*, 119:235901, 2016.